

Evaluating the Teaching-Learning Environment of Speaking Skills in English in the Odia Medium Secondary Schools through the Analysis of Textbooks and Opinion Polls

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Abstract

This paper analyzes two critical components associated with speaking skills in English, particularly of the students of Odia medium secondary school. Firstly, it comprehensively focuses on the chapters in the prescribed school textbooks, including grammar books for English, to examine the possible scope of activities related to the practice of speaking skills in English. Then, the data available from the responses of the students of different Odia medium schools of Odisha, opinions of parents and teachers of English collected in response to the semi-structured questionnaires provided to them have been presented in this chapter. Finally, a critical discussion has been made based on the survey's outcomes. It is noticed that the prescribed textbooks do not contain graded items enough for the practice of speaking skills. The students, teachers, and parents agree that there are lacunas associated with both socio-cultural, personal, and academic environments of the students that hinder them from obtaining the correct linguistic input and help develop the skills of speaking effectively by using correct lexical items as well as syntactic and pragmatic components in the basic discourse patterns required in academic and social contexts for the improvement of oral fluency.

Keywords: textbook, responses, socio-cultural, linguistic input, oral fluency

1. Introduction

Although there is a greater emphasis on improving spoken English, it is very often noticed that students of Odia medium schools in the State of Odisha, India, on average, do not possess the required fluency in speaking skills in English. The empirical evidence could be that academic and social environments are dominated by their respective mother tongue(s). So, the scope of speaking English is less. In addition, many other problems are associated with the system of acquisition of the English language, such as English being confined to the textbooks useful for appearing examinations primarily conducted in written form. The students are made to adopt rote learning methods without making consistent efforts to improve CALP and BICS. Right from the early stage of learning, students are not made aware of the segmental and suprasegmental components; the problem sounds for Odishan speakers of the English language, which is essential for the effectiveness of speech production and fluency.

1.1 English Textbook Evaluation Highlighting Speaking Activities

Second Language English (SLE) textbooks hold great importance in creating a better teaching-

learning process. This leads to creating the environment for second language assessment too. Most of the time, a well-designed textbook comes to be a handy tool and a much-valued reference for second language improvement. Assessing speaking skills concerning the prescribed textbooks' activities is a viable medium in this regard.

1.2 Importance of the Responses from Survey Poll

This inventory used for the survey poll is a self-report of the participants as responses to either statements or questions based on their experiences and realizations relating to the ESL learning in general and speaking skills in English. This kind of inventory creates an objective platform to identify the strategies used by the learners in English language learning. Such strategy inventory is a lucrative means to obtain empirical evidence in a threatening manner, and it is within the parameter of the research ethics not to force and motivate to obtain the possible answers as expected by the researcher.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Developing criteria for textbook evaluation
According to Williams (1983), there are four assumptions related to a set of linguistic, pedagogical, general, and technical criteria to evaluate a textbook in English as a second language (ESL). The ESL textbook should align with the methodology associated with psychological and linguistic principles. It is a complex task to fulfill the requirements in a multilingual setup. A scheme for evaluating ESLEFL textbook can be as follows:

Fig.1. Scheme for evaluating ESL/EFL textbooks
Linguistic/ Pedagogical

Basic Assumptions
General Speak Grammar
Vocabulary Reading
Writing Technical
Up-to-date method of L2 teaching

Guidance for non-native speakers of English

Need of the learners

Relevance of the socio-cultural environments

In Figure 1, the guidelines under the heading 'Linguistic/Pedagogical' entails methods of textbook production and selection and organization of skills and features of the language to be taught. This can be applicable for the textbooks written both for first or second-language speakers with keeping the following things in mind:

- a.the completeness and appropriateness of the items presented;
- b.the activities suggested for practicing the items selected;
- c.the sequencing of vocabulary, particularly the functional load, rate, and manner of entry and re-entry;
- d.the relevance of its contexts and situations, and so on (Tucker 1975) quoted in Williams, 83).

These criteria are derived from a combination of the linguistic and pedagogical components of

language teaching analysis (Halliday et al. 1964:207-22) quoted in Williams, 83)

'General' criteria embrace global considerations of methodology, and the needs of the learner, teacher, and community. 'Technical' criteria are concerned with the quality of editing and publishing, the availability of supplementary materials, cost and durability of the text, authenticity of language and style of the writer, etc.

The format can be followed to be suitable for particular contexts. For example, the suppositions about the non-native teacher, the needs of the learner, and the socio-cultural environment cannot be the same in Odisha as in Punjab.

2.2 Inventory Used for Survey in ESL

Oxford (1990) says strategic inventories are highly beneficial as they are easy and quick to administer. It is practically a nonthreatening means of reporting in a paper and pencil form, keeping confidentiality. However, in terms of validity and reliability, Ellis (1998) raises the point that the participants be self-conscious to provide systematic and complete data in this regard. Cohen (1998) also thinks that the participants' cognitive process is too complex and may not be comprehensive. Dorneyi (2001) also talks of the loss of motivation, the inability of double-checking the accuracy of the information, biased responses, and self-deception. However, as a matter of fact, this inventory has been designed on scientific, systematic, and well-framed statements as well as questions to get both general and specific information related to the speaking skills in English. Moreover, the Oxford (1989) 's Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) has been extensively used while preparing this.

3. Textbooks in English for Odia Medium Secondary School

As per the existing syllabus of the Government of Odisha, the following textbooks have been prescribed for the Odia medium secondary schools. A review of the contents in the light of the scopes of speaking skills has been presented here.

3.1 Class 8: A New Approach to English

The book has been prepared based on the pedagogic guidelines of the National Curriculum Framework (NCF, 2005). It has been tried out with real learners and teachers. It has been designed as learner-centric and has in-built tests to assess the performance of the learners. Language indicators are there for the inspection of parents and class inspectors. The book is designed strategically, adopting various methods and strategies such as Total Physical Response (TPR). There are mind-engaging activities. At first, there are three chapters on students' brush-up leading to proper lessons. The simplicity of language and interest of young learners of 12-13 years old have been emphasized. The editors have also emphasize learner-centred approaches based on brainstorming, chain-drill, VMDT (Visual Memory Development Technique), and Mental Talk (MT).

Part 1 of the book contains a chapter titled "Ali made impossible possible." There are pictographic interpretation, MCQ, text-content-based dialogue practice, and pronunciation of words with long vowels. Next, there are poems titled "Rainbow "and "Mongoose," which contain crossword V puzzles and vocabulary activities.

Part 2 of the book contains lessons in prose and poetry. There is a speaking activity in "The Riddle Master,"; read aloud activity in the poem "Accident"; dialogue practice in "The

Mountain and the Squirrel," "Day and Night," and "The Lost Camel." There is a chain drill in "Music Helps Plant Grow," "Scarecrow," and "Biju Pattanaik and His Dakotas."

Speaking skill-related hints in the book: It says three kinds of activities have been included: speaking and reading-aloud, chain-drill, and dialogue. Chain-drill is an utterance- a word, a phrase or a sentence, a line from a text or a title of story-which learners of a class repeat one after another in serial order, usually at the beginning or at the end of a lesson. Students can be asked to introduce themselves through a chain-drill. In addition, the rules of reading aloud have been given in the book. They are as follows:

Contents of the storybook include speaking dialogues in "Whose Horse Was It," "Six Wise Men," which are conversational. There are items for conversation in "The Thief and the Tiger" and "A wise grandmother," too.

3.2 Class -9 Grammar Textbook: The book Learn and Practise Grammar consists of twelve chapters elaborately dealing with sentence types, parts of a sentence, noun phrases, determiners, verbs, time and tense, auxiliaries and modals, adjectives, adverbs and adverbials, negatives and interrogatives and predicate phrases; a clear understanding and assimilation of the above items will equip the students with the ability and confidence to write and speak correctly.

Class-10 Grammar Book: The book has been designed to improve the ability of the secondary level students of Odisha to use English for academic and social purposes. Attempts have been made to use inductive learning, problem-solving activities, classroom competitions, and interactions. There are

activities encouraging self-learning outside the classroom. It also encourages self-discovery activities being supported by the respective facilitators. There are plans to integrate lessons from the book with other books of detailed and non-detailed studies. It starts with a revision of tenses.

3.3 Detailed study textbook for class-9: Skills of Communicative English for class-9

About the speaking skills, there are topics like "The Priceless Gift," which contains activities like writing the dialogues in the correct sequence, completing the dialogues; "An interview with the last moonwalker" is a conversational text; role-play in "Alexander Selkirk." There are no speaking activities in the non-detailed study.

Detailed Text for Class-10: Skills of Communicative English

Similarly, in this book, topics like "All things bright and beautiful (poem)," "A Letter to God," "We are Seven," "Tryst with Destiny," "Kapil Dev," "The Brook," "Air Pollution," and "School's Goodbye," there are listening and speaking activities. In "Village song," there is a group activity on speaking.

Apart from the textbooks, there are some additional activity-based books such as the Utkarsha Book designed especially for the improvement of the English language knowledge of the low-level proficiency students. The details of the books have presented below:

3.4 Utkarsha Book: The handbook has been developed to support individual students to reinforce the concepts, and practice skills learned during Utkarsh classes. There are speaking activities such as self-introduction(p.10), speaking activity(My Family, p.15); Worksheet-

20 has a speaking activity on describing objects through Q and A; ask the students to look at the pictures given below; ask them to name the things and then make a question about the object. (p.27). In Worksheet- 32, there is a speaking activity on daily routine (p.41). In the 'Supported Learning Phase' (p.60), there are activities related to daily short conversations. Some of them are as follows:

- i. You are late for class. Your teacher is in.
- ii. The teacher called your roll.
- iii. Somebody thanked you.
- iv. Somebody offers you chocolate. You do not want to take it.
- v. You want to use someone's pen.

From our analysis of the prescribed textbooks, it is noticed that there are not enough systematically prepared materials for the continuous practice of the speaking skills, which would improve the fluency and confidence of the students both in their respective academic and general domains.

4. Preparation of Survey Questionnaires, Sampling, and Participants

The objectives of the preparation and use of survey questionnaires are to get a clear picture of the opportunities and threats associated with ESL speaking skills of the secondary level Odia medium school students. This survey involves parents, teachers of English, and students. To make the survey meaningful in terms of giving result data, at least 16 experienced teachers (i.e., 4 each from coastal, eastern, western and southern) from different dialectal zones of Odisha have been chosen randomly. An equal number of parents has also been chosen based on random survey from such regions. Then, at least a total of 60 students, that is, 12 students from each of the zones, have been chosen from urban, semi-urban, and rural school set-ups. Separate

survey questionnaires were prepared for parents, teachers, and students as Strategy Inventory of Speaking Skills in ESL Survey (SISESLS) for obtaining information from various psychological, socio-cultural, pedagogic, and other domains.

While obtaining data from survey questionnaires, the researcher played the role of a facilitator helping the parents, teachers, and students understand the purpose and sharpen their responses based on the real problems associated with speaking skills in English.

4.1 Analysis of the Responses of the Students

After collecting responses from the students from different schools in Odisha, teachers of English, and some parents for the current study, the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Fig. 2 Region and Gender Ratio of the Participants

Sl.No.	Region of Odisha	No. of Participants	Ratio
1	South	15 (Male-9, Female-6)	60-40%
2	North	15 (Male-7), Female-8)	47-53%
3	Coastal	15 (Male-8, Female-7)	53-47%
4	West	15 (Male-6, Female-9)	40-60%

4.2 Modalities of the Inventory

Initially, a set of questions was prepared for the teachers of English working at secondary level Odia medium schools. The basis of preparing questions is mainly experiential and pedagogic reflections.

In the Indian context in general and specifically in the Odishan context, parents have got vital role to know about the achievements and failures of their wards in the academic

system they have undertaken. For that reason, there are some valuable questions in order to receive responses from parents. This includes questions based on their causes of satisfaction or dissatisfaction with the English language speaking skills. Then, other questions include regarding the pedagogic system, language speaking environment, methods and materials available, opportunities and threats, etc.

The SISELS set of survey questions/statements has been designed. The first is the demography of the respondents, which includes general background details like name, gender, and class. Then, introductory ice-breaking questions were asked, followed by questions based on strategies. They have been designed based on Cohen's Taxonomy of Strategies (1998). They are broadly divided into Language Learning Strategies (LLS) and Language Use Strategies (LUS). LUS is further sub-categorized into two parts: Retrieval and Rehearsal strategies. Under each category, there are at least two questions have been prepared.

4.3 Cognitive and Metacognitive Strategies

Cognitive strategies include practicing, analyzing expressions, and summarising. So, the questions based on this are: Do you practice newly learned words and expressions? Do you imitate the style and accent of the trainer/teacher? Do you structure your ideas and content before speaking? While speaking, do you record your speech for review later for improvement?

Metacognitive strategies include thinking about planning for learning, self-evaluation, and awareness regarding their doing and undoing.

83.3 % of students have a negative opinion of the first question, which is a matter to

be highlighted. In response to the second question, they admit that they lack opportunities to practice of speaking in English. This is also evident from our interaction with them. Then, significantly less number of students wait for a chance to speak in English whenever the opportunity comes. This might be because of a lack of confidence and practice. Similarly, 86.6% of students do not find a proper environment in socio-cultural and personal set-ups. The same is the case related to the last response, in which 90% of students do not create situations so that they can orally interact with people in English.

In this, students at an average opine that they practice new words and expressions that they have learned from textbooks and media sources. Nevertheless, number of non-practicing students is not less. 3.3% of students say that they practice only when required, which means they refer to classroom or examination requirements. Imitating the style of a teacher or trainer in speaking is also a good way of using words and expressions. Here, only 66.6% of students do that, whereas 10.6% of students do not do and 13.3% of students never mind that. Speech, conversation, and all such speaking activities are well communicated if both contents and expressions are well-organized. However, it is noticed that 75% of students cannot do that. 10% of students can develop their awareness regarding the structuring of ideas. Conversation practice is done through mirror practice. Some, however do it in a more effective way of recording a speech and reviewing it later. Here, 90% do not do that, which means this practice is not at all in use, which obviously hinders a self-learning technique. An active cognition strategy involves picturizing and decoding pictures in terms of words and expressions relevant to the contexts. Thus, 86% of students do not do that,

whereas 5% of students try to do that out of greater interest.

4.4 Affective and Social Strategies

Affective strategy refers to the emotional necessities of the learner, such confidence. They regulate the emotions, attitudes, motivations, and values of the learners of the language. It deals with psychological factors like mood, anxiety, feeling, and encouragement. The questions in this category could be i. I take a long breath to control my anxiety. ii. I listen to music to relax before doing a task.

86.6% of students cannot associate sounds while explaining some words. This shows that they are greatly confused regarding spelling and pronunciation. Only a negligible group of students, that is 6.6%, can follow this. Information retrieval through prompts in flashcards is a good classroom practice. However, it is noticed that 96.6% of students are not up to the mark. It seems there is no such regular classroom practice with flashcards.

Similarly, the description of objects is one of the primary measures of fluency which involves an organized way of describing an object plus the knowledge of the words used to describe different objects. In this, 16.6% of students claim to have the ability, whereas 78.3% do not have such ability. Nonverbal communication happens to be a primary means of conveying ideas. However, it is noticed that as many as 86.6% of students do not have such practices, whereas only 5% of the total students attempt to act out to convey ideas while speaking. 91.6% of students never have the self-initiative of speaking before the mirror in order to gain confidence. This shows that they are not self-motivated for this type of practice. 91.6% of students also do not make imaginary

conversation or rehearsal habits. While involved in the conversation, discourse fillers help us continue the conversation or talk better. As per data, 83.5% of students cannot do this because of a lack of stock vocabulary and confidence in doing so.

Contextual guessing of vocabulary is also an excellent way to speak out. 78.3% of students cannot do this because they lack mental repository of vocabulary. Around 8.3% of students hardly use such a technique in classroom activities. Self-encouragement for learning and improvement can be fruitful. However, in this case, it does not look very effective.

4.6 Retrieval and Rehearsal Strategies

Psychology plays a vital role in learning. Especially in the learning a second language, there are a series of tools and techniques such as mental codes to be devised by the learner. It involves memory, storage, and retrieval. Further, it plays a crucial role in connecting past information with the new information. Then, it establishes a link between ideas, emotions, and imaginations in multiple ways. Creating mental images, mental linkages between sounds and images, reviewing, grouping, regrouping, and structuring happen to be the works performed by the human mind (Oxford, 1990).

66.6% of students agree that they memorize sentences and conversation, which is short-term and hardly useful for the improvement of proficiency in speaking. However, 8.3% of students do so at times. Speaking without memorizing happens to be the natural process of competence. However, here, 76.6% of students say that they cannot speak in English without memorizing words, expressions, and sentences. 75% of students do not participate

in debating, group discussion, and rope-play like activities. These formal activities happen to be an integral part of the formal education process of second language learning. Students mostly do not find activities related to speaking skills in English textbooks. 93.3% of students do not find such activities in the school textbooks for which they do not have a scope of practicing routinely. In another way, since in multilingual contexts, translation from mother tongue to a target language is English takes place, many students utilize it as a tool. Here, in this context, 25% of students do so, whereas 56.6% of students do not take any such advantage. 50% of students find that their mother tongue creates problems in reaching a considerable level of proficiency in speaking. 33.3% of students find it no problem, whereas 25% of students do not even know if their mother tongue has any impact on English language learning or not.

4.7 Cover and Communication Strategies

4.7. Survey Report of Cover and Communication Strategies

In many situations, it is noticed that speakers reliably use synonymous words and expressions to convey meaning and ideas better. This is the strength of speech in the case of second language speakers. Here, 66.6% of students express their inability to use this tool, whereas only 21.6% of students can do this and 11.6% of students use to do it occasionally. This shows that they lack the clarity of concepts in this matter. Even 83.3% of students cannot correct mistakes and try to communicate by using alternative means of expressions. In contrast, non-verbal communication like the use of gestures, postures, signals, and symbols happen to be both supplementary as well as complimentary forms of expressions for bringing clarity in speaking skills. Here, it is noticed that 88.3% of students cannot take advantage of it.

Only 8.3% of the students make effective use of it which is negligible.

5. Survey Report from Teachers

The questions in this part of the survey have been prepared to obtain comprehensive and concrete information from the experienced practicing teachers of the Odia medium secondary schools of Odisha. Ten questions have been listed, covering all the parameters of applied linguistics associated with second language teaching and learning. They are based on communication skills, including L-S-R-W; segmental and suprasegmental elements of speech sounds; code-mixing and code-switching; mother tongue influence; translational competence; CALP and BICS, formal contexts of oral communication such as debating, role-play, group discussion, and question-answer, etc. It also covers vocabulary and daily life common expressions in English. Attention has also been given to psycholinguistic factors related to cognition and metacognition, short as well as long-term memory, and bilingualism and multilingualism as the potential resources of language learning and use.

Fig. 3 Region and Gender Ratio of the Participants

Sl.No.	Region of Odisha	No. of Participants	Ratio
1	South	15 (Male-9, Female-6)	60-40%
2	North	15 (Male-7), Female-8)	47-53%
3	Coastal	15 (Male-8, Female-7)	53-47%
4	West	15 (Male-6, Female-9)	40-60%

50% of the teachers agree that they deal with communication skills in an integrated way. Nevertheless, 37.5% do not follow that. They instead deal with the discrete language items, whereas 12.5% do it sometimes. 75% of the teachers find that students have pronunciation problems related to both consonant and vowel sounds, consonant clusters, and polysyllabic words. They find problems related to weak forms, contractions, pitch, contrastive stress, and intonation. There are also gross problems associated with code-switching, code-mixing, and translation from the mother tongue. 75% agree that while speaking English, the students are influenced by the pronunciation and intonation of their mother tongue.

However, 25% say that students follow the English stress and intonation. 87.5% of teachers say that the English textbooks do not have sufficient activities to improve speaking skills in English, both in academic and socio-cultural contexts. 12.5% of the teachers say that it is there, and the teachers can contextually devise activities on speaking skills. 93.75% find that students face difficulty speaking on academic topics fluently. They speak only mechanically. However, some of the students speak carefully when assigned certain topics. Even the same percentage of teachers agree that students cannot perform better in role-play, conversation, and other communicative activities, except some of the careful students who develop interest and overcome stage fright. In response to the seventh question, admittedly, all the teachers opine that students have poor vocabulary and they are unable to express everything in English except some broken speeches. 81.25% of teachers say that students cannot speak, translating their critical thinking

skills, emotions, attitudes, and imaginations into English. Only 6.25% say that students can do it because they have appropriate environments and personal interests. 81.25% of teachers say that students do not take the linguistic resources being bilinguals or multilingual. Some 6.25% of the teachers find that students can utilize such resources.

6. Survey Report from Parents

Questions asked in this survey of parents include exploration of confidence and fluency in English speaking skills, their knowledge related to prescribed textbooks in English, and possible speaking skills-related activities. Also, it includes questions seeking an opinion regarding the teaching-learning activities in a suitable environment and encouragement in terms of teaching-learning materials and resources related to improving speaking skills in English.

Fig. 4 Region and Gender Ratio of the Participants

Sl.No.	Region of Odisha	No. of Participants	Ratio
1	South	4 (Male-2, Female-2)	50-50%
2	North	4 (Male-2), Female-2)	-Do-
3	Coastal	4 (Male-2, Female-2)	-Do-
4	West	4 (Male-2, Female-2)	-50-

87.5% of the parents find that their children do not speak English well. However, 12.5% find that sometimes their children speak well. Similarly, 81.25% of parents do not express their satisfaction saying that there are not enough materials and activities designed to improve the speaking skills of the students, but 12.5% are still hopeful that textbooks can help improve their speaking skills. There are 6.25% of the

parents who are unaware of this. 87.5% of parents say that there is not enough classroom practice and teachers do not provide that much scope for improving speaking skills. Nevertheless, it may be pretty hopeful in some academic setups for which 6.25% of parents express their satisfaction with the classroom activities, and equal percentage of people seem to not know this. 93.75% of parents agree that there is no suitable social environment for the students to improve their communication skills. The rest of the parents, however do not possess that much idea regarding this. 81.5% of parents do not create scopes of encouraging their children to improve speaking skills. Only 6.25% of parents say that they provide such a scope but the rest 12.5%, do not have any such concern. 93.75% of parents do not provide materials for the improvement or creation of speaking skills. What is more, 6.25% of parents do not even have such an idea meant for their secondary school-going children.

7. Critical Discussion on the Responses

The analysis of data obtained from the textbooks of English responses of students, teachers, and parents reveals the fact that no such well-designed, scientific, sustainable, and result-oriented plans have been adopted so far for the improvement of the speaking skills of the students. In this context, focus on the theoretical perspectives of Vygotsky, Krashen, Oxford, Selinkar, and some others worth discussing. According to Krashen (2019):

... there are two independent systems of foreign language performance: 'the acquired system' and 'the learned system.' The 'acquired system' or 'acquisition' is the product of a subconscious process very similar to the process children undergo when acquiring their first language. It requires meaningful interaction in the target

language - natural communication - in which speakers are concentrated not in the form of their utterances but in the communicative act.

The "learned system" or "learning" is the product of formal instruction, and it comprises a conscious process that results in conscious knowledge 'about' the language, for example, knowledge of grammar rules. A deductive approach in a teacher-centered setting produces "learning," while an inductive approach in a student-centered setting leads to "acquisition." (<https://www.sk.com.br/sk-krash-english.html>)

Krashen thinks that:

... there is individual variation among language learners about 'monitor' use. He distinguishes those learners that use the 'monitor' all the time (over-users); those learners who have not learned or who prefer not to use their conscious knowledge (under-users); and those learners that use the 'monitor' appropriately (optimal users). An evaluation of the person's psychological profile can help determine to what group they belong. Usually, extroverts are under-users, while introverts and perfectionists are over-users. Lack of self-confidence is frequently related to the over-use of the "monitor." According to the input hypothesis, the learner improves and progresses along the 'natural order' when he/she receives second language 'input' that is one step beyond his/her current stage of linguistic competence. For example, if a learner is at a stage 'i', then acquisition occurs when he/she is exposed to 'Comprehensible Input' that belongs to level 'i + 1'. Since not all the learners can be at the same level of linguistic competence at the same time, Krashen suggests that natural communicative input is the key to designing a syllabus, ensuring in this way that each learner will receive some 'i + 1' input appropriate for his/her current stage of linguistic competence.

The Affective Filter hypothesis embodies Krashen's view that several 'affective variables' play a facilitative but non-causal, role in second language acquisition. These variables include motivation, self-confidence, anxiety, and personality traits. Krashen claims that learners with high motivation, self-confidence, a good self-image, a low level of anxiety, and extroversion are better equipped for success in second language acquisition. (<https://www.sk.com.br/sk-krash-english.html>)

It seems worthwhile to focus on Vygotsky's theory of speech production critically. According to McNeill (2000):

speech and gesture form a unit of thinking that he called growth point (GP), a notion closely connected to Vygotsky's concept of inner speech. The GP of an utterance combines "two distinct semiotic architectures"—one verbal and one imagistic—into a single meaning system. Importantly, because each component of the GP possesses "unique semiotic properties," each can surpass "the meaning possibilities of the other." (McNeill, 25)

McNeill & Duncan, 2000, (p. 144). Paraphrasing, Vygotsky, McNeill, and Duncan suggested that gestures are "material carriers of thinking" (p. 155) and therefore provide "an enhanced window into mental processes" (p. 144). In the context of gesture and thinking for speaking, they say that:

...in the activity of speaking, thinking takes on a particular quality as experiences are filtered through languages into verbalized events. He suggested that TFS might not merely influence how people talk about events but, more importantly, how they experience those events that "they are likely to talk about later."

According to Selinker (1972):

... learning strategies can be considered as belonging to the five psycholinguistic processes that shape the interlanguage system. These five psycholinguistic processes are as follows: native language transfer, overgeneralization of target language rules, transfer of training, strategies of communication, and strategies of learning. L2 learners use learning strategies as tactics to make the new cognitive demanding linguistic system simpler. (Selinker, 78)

In a similar vein, Ortega (2009) defined learning strategies as "conscious mental and behavioral procedures that individuals engage in intending to gain control over their learning process" (p. 208). To do so, teachers "must understand the philosophies and research that support and challenge the usefulness and educational value of each approach" (Herrera & Murry, 2011, p. 195). On the other hand, Kumaravadivelu (2001) points out that:

.... language teachers must not be just consumers of theories proposed by others rather than go beyond the limitations of these concepts with a call to "construct their context-sensitive pedagogic knowledge that will make their practice of everyday teaching a worthwhile endeavor" (p. 541). Educators are motivated to become post-method teachers or autonomous teachers capable of embarking on the continuous process of self-exploration and self-improvement. To do so, they are called to conduct teacher research which mainly involves observing, hearing, and reflecting on their daily teaching practices to identify the weaknesses and strengths of the pedagogy employed in the classroom. (Kumaravadivelu, 103).

8. Conclusion

Survey Questions for the students cover all the technical domains involving psychological, socio-cultural, and pedagogical factors associated with speaking skills. They include cognitive and met cognitive strategies, affective and social strategies, retrieval and rehearsal strategies, and cover and communication strategies. For parents and teachers of English, questions are based on the pedagogic, experiential, and environmental factors. It is worth saying that many students and their parents in the Odishan context as it is in the other Indian states, very frequently think of the improvement of speaking skills in English. Most rely on the classroom and academic institutional efforts to achieve this. However, it is clear that it needs combined, consistent and continuous efforts, which never happens in most cases. As discussed before, it requires regular, meaningful interaction in the target language; natural communication or communicative activities happen to be the dire need of the learners; approaches of teaching and learning should necessarily be inductive and student-centric; there should be a focus on individual variations among the language learners in order to make provisions for them to improve their speaking skills, and above all the speaking activities are required to a conscious mental and behavioral procedure.

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